

Supplemental Material:

Ex-ante measure of patent quality reveals intrinsic fitness for citation-network growth

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I. PATENT DATA: SOURCE & SELECTION

Data on attributes of patents and their citations used for our empirical analysis are sourced directly from the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) [S1]. Categorizations according to technological area are based on the Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC) system [S2], specifically its version published in November 2016. Based on the availability of patent grant data until the end of 2014, a typical grant lag extending for about 2-3 years, and a desired time window of 10 years for citation accrual, we decided to include only patents in our study that have been granted no later than during 2001. This year also coincides with the time when USPTO started publishing patent applications that are more than 18 months old, a policy change that likely affects the citation dynamics of more recently granted patents. We ensure having large-enough numbers of patents from individual CPC Sections by selecting patents granted between 1 Jan 1999 and 31 Dec 2001, which is still a narrow-enough range of time so that all patents in these cohorts were subject to basically the same external (legal, political, etc.) conditions. The relatively small number among them that either do not cite any USPTO patents or have a negative value for the variable BAG are excluded from further analysis, because their fitness variable would be undefined. Table SI lists basic summary statistics of the patent cohorts considered in this work.

II. SPECIFIC DETAILS FOR PATENT-QUALITY INDICATOR VARIABLES

A detailed overview of quantities that have been proposed as proxy measures of patent quality is given in Ref. [S3]. Here we comment only on specifics of such variables in the context of our study.

As we analyze cohorts of patents granted by the USPTO, BPA (BFP) corresponds to the number of backward citations to patents also granted by the USPTO (patents granted by other patent offices). Self-citations

are excluded from BPA. BAG is the arithmetic mean of the ages $T_i^{(a)} - T_j^{(g)}$ of all the patents j with grant dates $T_j^{(g)}$ cited by a new patent i (including self-citations) at the latter's time of application $T_i^{(a)}$. BCP of patent i is defined as

$$\text{BCP}_i = \left[\prod_{j=1}^{N_i} \frac{k_j(T_i^{(a)})}{\langle k(T_i^{(a)}) \rangle_{S_j}} \right]^{\frac{1}{N_i}}, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where N_i is the number of patents cited by patent i , and $k_j(T_i^{(a)})$ denotes the number of citations the cited patents j has at $T_i^{(a)}$. The citation counts of cited patents j are normalized by the average number $\langle k(T_i^{(a)}) \rangle_{S_j}$ of citations of patents from the same CPC Section S_j of patent j granted within the same three-month period. The originality of patent i is defined in analogy to Ref. [S4] as

$$\text{ORI}_i = 1 - \sum_C (P_C^{(i)})^2, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where $P_C^{(i)}$ is the portion of the N_i backward citations from patent i to other patents going into a given Class C from the CPC system. We utilize the information about all Classes a cited patent j is categorised into for calculating ORI, rather than just the first listed as was done in Ref. [S4]. Specifically, each cited patent j contributes to $P_C^{(i)}$ for each one of the $N_j^{(cl)}$ classes it is listed under with a value $(1/N_j^{(cl)}) \cdot (1/N_i)$. The variable CIN (INV, NCL) is obtained by subtracting the minimum required value 1 from the total number of independent claims (inventors, classes).

III. CITATION INFLATION

A trivial cause for temporal variations in citability arises from the, generally exogenously caused, changes in the rate of patent production. To be able to separate such effects from those reflecting the intrinsic properties of knowledge generation and diffusion, we renormalize a citation gained at a given time T to an equivalent citation at the fixed reference time T_0 via the ratio of patents applied for within a period ΔT from T_0 and T , respectively.

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TABLE SI. Summary statistics for patent cohorts analyzed in this work. These comprise USPTO patents granted during 1999-2001 within the individual listed CPC Sections that cite at least one USPTO patent ($BPA + BSC > 0$) and whose backward patent citations have non-negative average age ($BAG > 0$). Citations received from USPTO patents from any Section with application date within the 10-year period after the grant date of the cited patent are included. The value of each individual citation is adjusted to account for citation inflation as described in Sec. III.

CPC Section	A	B	C	F	G	H	Y
Number of patents in the cohort	79 961	98 138	66 545	45 282	118 730	113 223	91 657
Total of inflation-adjusted citations	1 545 480	998 751	697 685	374 499	2 019 315	1 738 541	1 228 236
Mean of inflation-adjusted citations	19.3	10.2	10.5	8.3	17.0	15.3	13.4
Median of inflation-adjusted citations	7.6	5.5	4.6	5.1	7.5	7.4	6.3

As the rate of patent production also differs across technology categories, this adjustment for citation inflation is performed separately for each CPC Section the citing patent is assigned to. More specifically, a citation from patent j that has been applied for at time $T_j^{(a)}$ and was assigned to the set $\{S\}_j$ of CPC Sections is counted with an inflation-adjusted value

$$c_j(T_j^{(a)}; T_0, \Delta T) = \frac{1}{|\{S\}_j|} \sum_{S \in \{S\}_j} \frac{N_S(T_0, \Delta T)}{N_S(T_j^{(a)}, \Delta T)}. \quad (\text{S3})$$

Here $N_S(T, \Delta T)$ denotes the number of patents from CPC Section S applied for during the period $[T, T + \Delta T]$, and $|\{S\}_j|$ is the cardinality of the set $\{S\}_j$. In our study, $T_0 = 1$ Jan 1999 and $\Delta T = 3$ months. Figure S1 shows the time variation for inflation-adjusted values of citations from patents assigned to a single CPC Section.

FIG. S1. Value $c(T; T_0, \Delta T)$ of an inflation-adjusted citation made at time T by patents assigned to individual CPC Sections, corresponding to the ratio of the numbers of patents from a given CPC Section that were applied for in the time intervals $[T_0, T_0 + \Delta T]$ and $[T, T + \Delta T]$, respectively. The value of a citation from a patent assigned to more than one CPC Section is calculated as the average of their associated citation values. Here $T_0 = 1$ Jan 1999 and $\Delta T = 3$ months.

IV. FITTING EMPIRICAL CITATION RATES

To analyze the empirical data for citation rates in their dependence on k and t , we place each patent in a particular bin based on its number k_i of citations accrued at the end of each time period. The binning in the time dimension is linear with bin width $\Delta t = 3$ months. In the k dimension, partial logarithmic binning is used [S5], i.e., each k bin has the same width on a logarithmic scale for values of $k > 5$. (Setting a minimum for k is necessary to eliminate discretization effects inherent in citation accrual.) The logarithmic-bin width is chosen such that the amount of data in each bin is sufficiently large for statistical accuracy. Assuming the functional form given in Eq. (1) of the main paper, with Eqs. (6a) and (6b), the corresponding dependences on k and t are fitted to the

FIG. S2. Empirically extracted ageing functions typically show the behavior illustrated in Fig 2(a) from the main paper. Deviations of the kind shown here occur sporadically, and mostly for the large- k bins where statistical accuracy is limited due to the relatively small numbers of patents in them. As in Fig. 2(a) from the main paper, we show here fits of exponential-ageing functions to both the fitness-controlled citation rate $\lambda_i/\eta_i \equiv [\Delta k_i(t + \Delta t)/\eta_i]/\Delta t$ (data points indicated by triangles) and the uncontrolled-for-fitness average citation rate $\bar{\lambda}_i \equiv \Delta k_i(t + \Delta t)/\Delta t$ (data points indicated by circles) at fixed k . Data shown here are for the $k = 27$ bin of USPTO patents from CPC Section A granted during 1999-2001.

TABLE SII. Technology-classification dependence of parameters associated with preferential attachment ($\tilde{\alpha}_0$, $\tilde{\alpha}_\infty$, \tilde{f}_0) and ageing ($\tilde{\tau}$, \tilde{A}_0) in the citation rate given by Eq. (1) in the main paper, in conjunction with Eqs. (6a) and (6b). For comparison, parameters in the uncontrolled-for-fitness average rate $\tilde{\lambda}_i \equiv (k_i^\alpha + f_0) A_0 \exp\{-t/\tau\}$ fitted to the data are also included. We give both the saturation value $\tilde{\alpha}_\infty$ (the weighted average of the latest third among the extracted values for $\tilde{\alpha}$ and the value $\tilde{\alpha}_0$ for $t = 0$ (corresponding to the time of grant)). The time $\tilde{\tau}$ given here is the weighted average of obsolescence times extracted for the fixed- k bins. For reference, the empirically extracted standard deviation $\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}$ of the log of fitness η is also given. The values for $\tilde{A}(0)\tilde{f}(0)$ are obtained from the time evolution of the fraction of uncited patents [Eq. (4) from the main paper]. Comparing these with $\tilde{A}_0\tilde{f}_0$ provides a satisfactory consistency check for demonstrating the overall suitability of our approach.

CPC Section	A	B	C	F	G	H	Y
$\tilde{\alpha}_0$	0.65 ± 0.09	0.76 ± 0.10	0.73 ± 0.08	0.81 ± 0.20	0.70 ± 0.03	0.69 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.05
$\tilde{\alpha}_\infty$	0.82 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.04	0.83 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.07	0.89 ± 0.04	0.89 ± 0.04	0.84 ± 0.03
α	1.13 ± 0.03	1.10 ± 0.06	1.11 ± 0.04	1.14 ± 0.07	1.10 ± 0.08	1.10 ± 0.06	1.10 ± 0.03
\tilde{f}_0	1.14 ± 0.13	1.33 ± 0.18	1.01 ± 0.16	1.87 ± 0.52	1.16 ± 0.17	1.14 ± 0.15	1.15 ± 0.13
f_0	1.32 ± 0.43	1.48 ± 0.62	1.05 ± 0.27	1.64 ± 0.66	1.22 ± 0.48	1.31 ± 0.37	1.35 ± 0.43
$\tilde{\tau}$ (yr)	7.53 ± 2.92	7.12 ± 1.97	6.50 ± 1.33	7.37 ± 2.08	6.16 ± 2.82	6.15 ± 2.73	7.03 ± 1.51
τ (yr)	5.25 ± 0.54	5.47 ± 0.63	5.12 ± 0.48	5.84 ± 0.67	5.19 ± 1.21	5.25 ± 0.93	5.45 ± 0.41
\tilde{A}_0 (yr ⁻¹)	0.54 ± 0.08	0.35 ± 0.05	0.54 ± 0.05	0.30 ± 0.03	0.35 ± 0.08	0.34 ± 0.07	0.40 ± 0.04
A_0 (yr ⁻¹)	0.33 ± 0.04	0.26 ± 0.03	0.31 ± 0.04	0.23 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.05	0.22 ± 0.05	0.27 ± 0.02
$\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}$	0.74	0.58	0.80	0.69	0.61	0.55	0.60
$\tilde{A}(0)\tilde{f}(0)$ (yr ⁻¹)	0.49 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.01	0.50 ± 0.01	0.55 ± 0.01	0.60 ± 0.01	0.49 ± 0.01

averages $[\overline{\Delta k_i(t + \Delta t)/\eta_i}]/\Delta t$ over patents in the fixed- t , fixed- k bins using a weighted non-linear logarithmic regression. The empirical proxy $\overline{\Delta k_i(t + \Delta t)/\Delta t}$ for the uncontrolled-for-fitness citation rate $\tilde{\lambda}$ is treated analogously. Results obtained from this fitting are illustrated in Figs. 2 and 3 from the main paper. See also Table SII for numerical values of relevant quantities and additional information. Sporadic deviations from the typically observed exponential ageing behaviour are shown in Fig. S2.

V. EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS FOR MINIMIZING CROSS-CORRELATIONS

A. Motivation

The raw quality-indicator variables $v^{(a)}$ listed in Table I from the main paper are *ad-hoc* choices based on their known characteristics [S3] and availability for any patent at the time of grant. Each of them on its own can be expected to be a partial proxy measure for the fitness parameter η that quantifies patents' attractiveness for being cited. To gain an overall better quantification for η , we devise a way to meaningfully combine the observations for all the 13 variables from the main paper's Table I. As a first step, we define normalized variables $\bar{v}^{(a)}$ via Eq. (2) given in the main paper. Applying the log-transformation to all $v^{(a)}$ except originality is motivated by the observation that these variables are close to being log-normally distributed like many performance-indicator-type quantities from various fields [S6–S9]. As

all the $\bar{v}^{(a)}$ are approximately normally distributed with zero mean and unit variance, we can use an exploratory factor analysis [S10] to minimize cross-correlations between their respective measures of patent quality. Factors are extracted via a principal factor analysis (also known as principal axis factoring) [S11].

B. Selection and rotation of principal factors

It is generally advised that the selection of the principal factors should be done by Horn's parallel analysis [S12]. However, for extremely large sample sizes as in the patent cohorts considered here, this methodology is almost indistinguishable from the Kaiser criterion [S13]. Hence, we use the latter threshold for practical purposes; i.e., we keep factors with eigenvalues greater than zero. We then implement a varimax rotation [S14], which maximises the squared loadings that make up each factor while ensuring that the vectors remain orthogonal. (Performing an orthogonal, rather than the more typically applied oblique, rotation is mandated by our purpose to find minimally correlated factors that measure patent quality and construct the fitness parameter governing citation dynamics as their linear combination.) This process acts to reduce the number of high factor loadings while increasing the number of near-zero loadings. In principle, we could use the results from our factor analysis to compare the different latent factors that are related to technological impact for different types of inventions, but our methodology is not optimised for this purpose.

C. Determining factor scores for individual patents

Having obtained the factors $\bar{u}^{(b)}$, we now would like to construct factor scores for every patent in the given cohort in terms of values for the original variables $\bar{v}^{(a)}$. We perform a standard regression to address the factor-indeterminacy problem [S15], which is a procedure generally referred to as *Thomson scoring* [S16, S17], and normalize each factor variable to have unit variance. This yields the final factor loadings $L_a^{(b)}$ that relate individual factor scores $\bar{u}_i^{(b)}$ for patent i to the observed values $\bar{v}_i^{(a)}$ of the input variables via

$$\bar{u}_i^{(b)} = \sum_a L_a^{(b)} \bar{v}_i^{(a)} \quad . \quad (\text{S4})$$

Figure 1(a) in the main paper shows the loadings values $L_a^{(b)}$ for the 6 factors obtained when analysing the cohort of patents from CPC Section A granted during 1999-2001. Corresponding results for the other cohorts considered in this work are shown in Fig. S3. The sign of the loadings is fixed by our convention (see more detailed explanation below) that the factors correlate positively with an increased number of citations accrued by the time of grant in a small training dataset.

D. Comment regarding sampling adequacy

In typical factor-analytical studies, the commonly reported Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy [S18] is given as an indicator of ‘factorial simplicity’ for a particular variable. This measure is maximized when a variable has a non-zero loading on only one factor. Hence, it is a way to quantify how useful particular variables are in determining the meaning of extracted factors. The KMO is then averaged over all variables as a way of measuring this ‘simplicity’. In our work, the KMO is between 0.62 and 0.68 for each of the patent cohorts. KMO values of this magnitude indicate that only large

TABLE SIII. Fraction r^2 of variability explained by the quantities $\bar{v}^{(a)}$ in the log of citation counts accrued at time t after their time of grant by USPTO patents from indicated CPC Sections granted during 1999-2001, and the proportion r_u^2/r^2 of this explained variability that is able to be captured by the set of factors $\bar{u}^{(b)}$ chosen via the stepwise regression.

t (yr)	Section	A	B	C	F	G	H	Y
0	r^2	0.17	0.14	0.13	0.08	0.27	0.27	0.22
	r_u^2/r^2	0.95	0.92	0.87	0.93	0.91	0.93	0.96
5	r^2	0.26	0.20	0.19	0.15	0.29	0.26	0.26
	r_u^2/r^2	0.94	0.87	0.87	0.86	0.84	0.86	0.94
10	r^2	0.28	0.20	0.19	0.16	0.29	0.25	0.26
	r_u^2/r^2	0.94	0.87	0.87	0.84	0.82	0.85	0.93

or consistent differences between factors and technology categories should be taken seriously for any statistically relevant interpretation. We quote the KMO values here only for general information, as finding and interpreting the latent factors affecting our variables is not the primary goal of this work. As we use factor analysis only as a tool to reduce cross-correlations between variables that determine the fitness variable for citation-network growth, the KMO values are actually not relevant for our purposes. Exploration of the interesting variation between factor composition across different technology categories that is apparent from Fig. S3 will be left for future study.

VI. FROM QUALITY FACTORS TO FITNESS

A. Determining relative factor weights

Performing the factor analysis described in the preceding Section has yielded the factors $\bar{u}^{(b)}$ as the minimally correlated superpositions of the normalized patent-quality indicator variables $\bar{v}^{(a)}$. We intend to use these quality factors to gain a proxy measure for the unobserved fitness variable η that quantifies the intrinsic attractiveness for patents to be cited, according to the form of Eq. (1) in the main paper. To this end, we determine the weights w_b of factors $\bar{u}^{(b)}$ in their combination that is most highly correlated with citation growth at early times by running a forward-stepwise ordinary least squares regression on a randomly selected small training dataset with the Bayes Information Criterion (BIC) [S19] as our test statistic and the log of the (mean-scaled) citations at grant as the dependent variable. Figure 1(b) in the main paper shows the weights obtained for the cohort of patents from CPC Section A granted during 1999-2001. Corresponding results for the other cohorts are given in Fig. S4. Note that, due to the stepwise nature of the regression, some factors never add enough information (as measured by the BIC) to be included in the fitness metric [S20]. We furthermore adopt the convention where $w_b \geq 0$ by absorbing the sign of the regression coefficients into the definition of the factors $\bar{u}^{(b)}$ in terms of the variables $\bar{v}^{(a)}$. This fixes the sign of the loadings $L_a^{(b)}$ shown in Fig. S3 and in Fig. 1(a) of the main paper.

As the training dataset comprises only $\sim 10\%$ of patents from any given cohort (which are also subsequently excluded from further analyses), and the dependent variable is determined by the citation count at only one point in time, this procedure does not preordain the functioning of our approximation for the citation-related fitness parameter across the entire cohort and for the entire ten-year time period for which forward-citation accrual is analyzed. And while our choice of using citation counts at the time of grant is motivated by the desire to minimize possible influences of knowledge diffusion on the construction of the fitness parameter, using the log of citation counts at a later time as the dependent vari-

FIG. S3. Factors and associated loadings $L_a^{(b)}$ obtained from the exploratory factor analyses performed on patent-quality indicator variables for cohorts of patents granted during 1999-2001 within the specified CPC Sections. The order of factors from left to right in each panel corresponds to the order of decreasing eigenvalue, i.e., variance, associated with the factors.

able in the weight-determining regression for the given set of chosen factors does not yield significantly different results. Table SIII lists the fraction r^2 of variability in the dependent variable (i.e., log of citation counts for patents from a given cohort at a given time t after their time of grant) explained by all of the normalized quality-indicator variables $\bar{v}^{(a)}$, alongside the proportion r_u^2/r^2 of the explained variability retained in the given set of selected factors. The factors are able to adequately represent the total variability in citation counts associated with the quality-indicator variables known at time

of grant, with the goodness of fit r_u^2/r^2 generally decreasing only slightly for later t . In the cases where r^2 is seen to increase with t , this most likely reflects a reduction of granularity in the data by the increased spread of citation counts among patents in these cohorts.

Using the weights w_b obtained by the procedure described above, we propose to estimate the fitness variable η in terms of the quality-indicator factors via

$$\ln(\eta) = -\frac{\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}^2}{2} + \frac{\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}}{\sqrt{\sum_b w_b^2}} \sum_b w_b \bar{u}^{(b)} \quad , \quad (\text{S5})$$

FIG. S4. Weights w_b for the factors entering the fitness parameter to describe citation growth for the cohorts of patents granted during 1999-2001 within the specified CPC Sections. Numbers labeling individual factors for a particular cohort correspond to those from Fig. S3. Missing factors were eliminated during regression according to the Bayes Information Criterion.

equivalent to Eq. (5) in the main paper. The so-defined fitness variable η has the distribution $\rho(\eta) = \text{Lognormal}(-\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}^2/2, \sigma_{\ln(\eta)}^2)$ and satisfies $\mu_\eta = 1$. The only missing ingredient is the empirical value of $\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}$.

B. Extracting $\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}$ from citation data

In the following, we consider the dynamics of how patents acquire their first citation by looking at the time evolution of the fraction $n(0, t)$ of uncited patents. We focus on the short-time limit where the patents accruing citations will generally be those having a well-above-noise level of intrinsic fitness. Our method for determining $\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}$ is thus immune to any influence from the, likely anomalous [S21, S22], subset of never-cited patents.

The fraction $n_\eta(0, t)$ of uncited patents with fixed fitness η in some cohort satisfies the Master equation [S23]

$$\frac{dn_\eta(0, t)}{dt} = -\lambda(0, t) n_\eta(0, t) \quad . \quad (\text{S6})$$

Assuming the citation rate to be of the form $\lambda(k, t) = \eta \tilde{A}(t) \tilde{f}(k)$, we find [S23]

$$n_\eta(0, t) = \exp \left\{ -\eta \tilde{f}(0) \int_0^t dt' \tilde{A}(t') \right\} \quad . \quad (\text{S7})$$

For a cohort where patents with fitness η are distributed according to the distribution $\rho(\eta)$, the general form given in Eq. (3) from the main paper (see also Ref. [S24]) is obtained for the fraction

$$n(0, t) \equiv \int d\eta \rho(\eta) n_\eta(0, t) \quad (\text{S8})$$

of uncited patents in the entire cohort. Expanding the exponential on the r.h.s. of this expression yields

$$n(0, t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{E[\eta^m]}{m!} \left\{ -\tilde{f}(0) \int_0^t dt' \tilde{A}(t') \right\}^m \quad (\text{S9})$$

in terms of the moments $E[\eta^m]$ of the fitness distribution $\rho(\eta)$. For our particular case of interest, we have $\rho(\eta) = \text{Lognormal}(-\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}^2/2, \sigma_{\ln(\eta)}^2)$ and thus obtain

$$n(0, t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{\exp \left\{ \frac{m(m-1)}{2} \sigma_{\ln(\eta)}^2 \right\}}{m!} \left[-\tilde{f}(0) \int_0^t dt' \tilde{A}(t') \right]^m \quad (\text{S10})$$

Focusing on the time evolution of uncited patents has the advantage that it is insensitive to the actual k dependence of $\tilde{f}(k)$. For any sufficiently well-behaved ageing function $\tilde{A}(t)$, Eq. (S10) can be calculated and compared with empirical data. However, for our purposes, we do not want to prejudice the estimate for the fitness variable by any *ad-hoc* assumption about ageing. We there-

FIG. S5. Log-linear plot of the fraction $n(0, t)$ of uncited USPTO patents assigned to CPC Section A with grant date during 1999-2001 as a function of time t measured from each individual patent's time of grant. The approximation $n_{\text{fit}}(0, t)$ given in Eq. (S10) obtained from fitting the line shape of $n(0, t)$ around the inflection point at $t = t_*$ is used to extract the standard deviation $\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}$ of the log of fitness. The time t_0 is determined via the extrapolation $n_{\text{fit}}(0, t_0) \equiv 1$.

fore consider the short-time limit where $\tilde{A}(t) \approx \tilde{A}(0)$ and, hence, the expression in Eq. (S10) provides the Taylor expansion for $n(0, t)$ in the variable t with only two independent parameters; $\tilde{A}(0)\tilde{f}(0)$ and $\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}^2$. Equation (4) from the main paper shows the resulting expansion of $\ln n(0, t)$ upto second order in t that could ideally be fitted to the citation data and yield empirical values for these parameters. In practice, the fact that patents generally already acquire examiner citations and self-citations before the time of grant means that $n(0, 0) < 1$, necessitating a modified approach.

Figure S5 illustrates the typically observed time evolution of $n(0, t)$. The rate at which patents accrue their first citation, and $n(0, t)$ concomitantly decreases, is initially slow. A marked increase in the rate is observed

for $t_0 \lesssim t < t_*$, after which the decrease of $n(0, t)$ slows again. Finding the slope \bar{t}^{-1} at the inflection point t_* that separates the regions of accelerated and later slowed decrease in the observed $n(0, t)$ and fitting the $n(0, t)$ curve to quadratic order in the vicinity of t_* yields the approximation

$$n_{\text{fit}}(0, t) = \exp \left\{ -\frac{t-t_0}{\bar{t}} \Theta(t-t_0) + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \frac{(t-t_*)^2}{\bar{t}^2} \Theta(t-t_*) \right\}. \quad (\text{S11})$$

Motivated by the theoretical result for the short-time limit of $n(0, t)$ given in Eq. (4) from the main paper, we identify $\bar{t} \equiv 1/[\tilde{A}(0)\tilde{f}(0)]$ and $\varepsilon = \exp\{\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}^2\} - 1$. The fact that t_* turns out to be within 2-6 months from the date of grant indicates that the so-determined $\sigma_{\ln(\eta)}$ appropriately reflects the short-time behavior considered in the model leading to Eq. (4) in the main paper.

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- [S20] Exclusion of factors by the stepwise regression procedure based on BIC ensures a minimal level of noise in our conservative estimate of the true fitness. As the number of factors is smaller by a factor of 10^{-4} than the number of observations in the training dataset, we are well below the threshold that has been suggested to avoid loss of predictability when using this method [S25, S26].
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